

FISCAL POLICY AND ITS ROLE IN REDUCING UNEMPLOYMENT IN IRAQ FOR THE PERIOD 2004-2020

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ABSTRACT

Given the role of fiscal policy in achieving goals through public expenditures and revenues on the unemployment rate, which is an important and basic indicator in the economy of any country, and accordingly, the research was divided into a theoretical aspect to clarify the basic concepts of fiscal policy and unemployment, its causes and the most important types, and an applied section to analyze the development of public revenues and expenditures and analyze Unemployment rates during the research period (2004-2020), and the research reached a number of conclusions, the most important of which is that the increase in real public expenditures in any year leads to a decrease in unemployment rates, which shows the role played by fiscal policy as one of its tools to reduce unemployment rates, and highlights the main objective To research, study the developments of the financial policy in the Iraqi economy in the aspect of the general budget (expenditures and revenues) and its impact on the level of unemployment by reducing the phenomenon of unemployment in Iraq.

Keywords: Unemployment rate, general revenue, overhead

Introduction

Fiscal policy is one of the most important means for the state to intervene in economic activity, to achieve the multiple objectives pursued by the macro economy and to address the crises it is exposed to, due to its close relationship in all aspects of economic life and its impact on economic development and achieving prosperity. In addition to achieving economic stability and social justice. It is one of the foundations on which economic management depends in both developed and developing countries, and the advanced level that many economic systems have reached, especially the developed countries, which have contributed directly and indirectly to the development of those countries and this is a fact that cannot be ignored.

If the financial policies showed the economic superiority of these countries in all fields, and these developments call for a study of the nature of the financial policy in those developed countries, and an attempt to benefit from the theories of those policies and their application in developing countries, provided that these policies are real tools that contribute to achieving development and alleviating unemployment. in developing countries. Therefore, in this research, the concepts and definitions of fiscal policy will be studied through a statement of the definition and tools of fiscal policy and its objectives, and on the other hand, the study of the effectiveness of fiscal policy and its impact on overcoming the level of unemployment in Iraq.

Research importance:

The importance of research is to know the effectiveness of fiscal policy in treating economic imbalances and problems, especially since Iraq is among the developing countries that suffer from unemployment.

Research goal:

The problem of unemployment is one of the most important problems that receive the attention of economists, politicians and other groups of society, so the problem revolves around the extent of the effectiveness of fiscal policy in Iraq in addressing the problem of unemployment through the revenues obtained by the state and the expenditures spent by the state in influencing the volume of unemployment in Iraq for the period (2004). -2020).

Research Hypothesis

The research is based on the hypothesis that the fiscal policy in Iraq has an impact on macroeconomic variables in general and unemployment in particular, and this effect produces different results in terms of positive or negative on the economy as a whole, according to the different circumstances experienced by the Iraqi economy.

Research Structure

The research was divided into three axes. In the first axis, we dealt with the theoretical framework of financial policy and unemployment. In the second axis, we dealt with the analysis of public expenditures and public revenues in Iraq. The research concludes in the third axis, which includes the analysis of unemployment rates in Iraq.

The first axis: the theoretical framework for fiscal policy and unemployment

1-The concept of fiscal policy: Fiscal policy is also known as an analytical study of the financial activity of the public sector in all its branches, as it includes a quantitative adjustment to the volume of public spending and public revenues, and the achievement of other goals to advance the wheel of development, advance the national economy, achieve justice among members of society, achieve economic stability and reduce income disparity. Between high and low incomes (Al-Qaisi, 2015: 83).

It is also defined as all the procedures and trends adopted and followed by the state in influencing society and the national economy, which would achieve the goals of social and economic development (Al-Wadi, 2015: 190).

Fiscal policy is defined as a set of tools that are used to move the general budget tools to achieve balance at the price level, the level of full employment and an acceptable economic growth rate (Savin, 2009: 285).

2 - Objectives of the fiscal policy: There is a set of objectives that the fiscal policy seeks to achieve, namely:

2-1: Economic stability Economic stability is intended to achieve the highest level of full employment, that is, to achieve the largest level of material product or real national income,

which means a high level of employment without inflation, i.e. maintaining a stable level of prices, as the fiscal policy during a period of Inflation by imposing increasing taxes, which works to reduce government spending, that is, the attempt to absorb excess purchasing power and reduce aggregate demand. In a period of depression, fiscal policy reduces taxes and increases government spending, in order to increase the level of aggregate demand and that the goal of this policy is to achieve economic stability. Without these policies, the economy goes into strong problems and fluctuations, and may even suffer from inflation and unemployment, and this is done through the use of fiscal policy tools to influence aggregate demand (**Al-Jubouri and Al-Zaidi, 2014: 595-639**).

2-2- Redistribution of income: It is one of the most important tools through which the state can achieve justice in the distribution of income and wealth among individuals, by imposing progressive taxes on those with high incomes and imposing other indirect taxes that are of high prices on luxury goods. Goods are consumed by those with high incomes, and the proceeds of these taxes are redirected through the spending policy of the economy, and then they are spent on various areas such as health, education, providing social benefits through social security, and providing economic subsidies to support the prices of necessary commodities that benefit low-income earners. As for the developing countries, income distribution requires a set of economic and social goals to be redistributed, including that the equitable distribution of income is one of the means of achieving social stability among the different classes of society first, and achieving political stability through the absence of strikes, demonstrations, protests and others secondly. (**Shendi and Najm, 2015: 1-21**).

2-3- Increasing economic growth rates: growth, which is defined as (a process intended to achieve a cumulative and continuous increase in real income, as this increase is greater than the increase in the population with the availability of productive and social services and the provision of protection for renewable resources from pollution, as well as the preservation of on non-renewable resources). Investment has a major role in advancing economic growth, as indicated by some theories, and that government investments are part of those total investments, and therefore they are to drive economic growth. (**Nasser & Hadi, 2019: 1-13**).

2-4- Achieving the level of full employment: It means achieving the level of full employment of the productive capacity available in society, and that the focus to achieve this goal was and still is the goal of every government in different countries, and this became clear after the Great Depression, and thus fiscal policy has a clear and important role in Attempting to reduce unemployment, by increasing government spending or reducing taxes in order to try to raise the level of effective demand, which leads to an increase in the level of demand for work, and this in turn leads to an increase in the real national income (**Al-Adara and Al-Assami, 2020: 1-30**).

3 - Financial Policy Tools: Financial policy uses many tools through which it can implement its goals that it seeks to achieve through several tools, namely:

3-1- Public expenditures: It is one of the most important means of financial policy used that shows the state's economic role and the extent of its intervention in economic activity. Public

expenditure is defined as the sum of money used by the state or one of its institutions to satisfy public needs (Al-Omari, 1988: 23). And public spending varies from one country to another according to the nature of the economic system. In capitalist countries, public spending aims to achieve economic stability, and then reduce unemployment, tackle inflation, and activate and expand the local market, while spending in developing countries aims to form an advanced industrial production apparatus. As well as providing consumer goods to individuals, and the policy through which the government spends on various aspects is called public expenditure, which can be defined as an amount of money spent by the state to achieve a public benefit **(Abdul Hadi and Hassoun, 2021: 66-79)**.

3-2- Public Revenues: Public revenue is the second main tool of fiscal policy. These revenues lie with the government to perform its multiple functions, given the development and expansion caused by the increase in public expenditures, which was reflected in the diversification, development and increase of types of public revenue. Taxes are one of the most important types of revenue. The relative importance of taxes has increased, whether in developed or developing countries, and there are many types of taxes, whether direct or indirect taxes, through which the state can control the national economy. Local industries from foreign competition impose a high customs tax, and if the goal of the tax is to reduce income disparity, progressive taxes are imposed to reduce differences between individuals **(Bakhit and Matar, 2012: 189-224)**.

4- Unemployment: its concept, types and causes

4-1- Unemployment: There is a comprehensive definition of unemployment recommended by the International Labor Organization that the unemployed person is that individual who is above a certain age without work and is able and willing and looking for it at the prevailing wage level, and to clarify the unemployment rate based on the percentage of the number of unemployed people who are able to work To the total labor force, the unemployment rate (the number of unemployed people who are able to work / the total labor force) x 100 **(Hussain, 2012: 80-107)**. Unemployment leads to an increase in the deficit in the balance of payments and the general budget and also leads to social, family and psychological suffering as a result of deprivation and suffering that may push the individual to drug and alcohol abuse, violence and crime, or to emigrate; Therefore, we find that the studies on unemployment do not include the important aspect of the actually unemployed, because of the difference between the unemployed groups, as these groups vary in terms of the length of the unemployment period, the extent of the high unemployment rate and the extent of suffering from it, and calculating the unemployment rate based on age or region Geographical or gender shows completely different results on the overall unemployment rate.

There are two basic conditions for defining the unemployed in terms of official statistics, which are **(Al-Shammari, 2013: 131-150)**:

- 1- That the unemployed person is able to work.
- 2- The unemployed person is looking for a job opportunity.

4-2- Types of unemployment: Unemployment is classified into several types, including (Al-Najm, 2019: 426-440):

1. Structural unemployment: It arises from shifts in demand or changes in technology so that the labor force, through its qualifications and experience, is consistent with the demand in the labor market.
2. Cyclical unemployment: It appears as a result of economic fluctuations and disappears with the transition of the economy to a state of prosperity or prosperity.
3. Frictional unemployment: It occurs as a result of the movement of workers from one job to another.
4. Disguised unemployment: It occurs when the marginal product of the worker is zero or negative, and it appears in the agricultural sector and is widespread in developing countries.
5. Seasonal unemployment: It appears due to the varying seasons and the nature of work.

4-3- Causes of unemployment: There are many factors that cause unemployment or exacerbate it, the most prominent of which are (Lashmari, 2013: 131-150):

The state's programs focus on the transition to a market economy and the accompanying structural changes in the Iraqi economy.

- 1- Most of the public sector companies stopped working and a significant decrease in the production capacities of some of them.
- 2- The inability of the private sector to take a role in the economy due to the weakness of capital and the flight of many abroad.
- 3- Security and political instability, as well as the administrative and financial corruption that is prevalent in most state institutions.
- 4- Openness to imported goods and the policy of dumping, which exhausted the Iraqi economy by the role of the neighborhood, led to the cessation of most of the small and medium industries.

The second axis: analysis of public expenditures and public revenues in Iraq

1- Public spending analysis: It is one of the pillars on which economic development rests, as the increase in public expenditures in the state has become a natural matter according to different systems, and that public spending is an essential part of the state's financial policy, and the change that occurred in the philosophy of governance in Iraq after (2003) And the transition of the Iraqi economy from an interfering socialist system to a free market system, and Iraq adopted the philosophy of economic freedom and the market economy system, and the observer of Iraq's budgets notes that government expenditures during the study period were in an upward direction in an attempt to improve the living and conditions of the Iraqi citizen by increasing spending on (support for derivatives Oil, subsidizing the ration card for individuals, raising spending on social protection networks, and creating job opportunities through recruitment in the public sector, especially the military forces of all kinds) and this

appears through salaries and wages, which make up the largest percentage of spending (Ahmed, 2019: 116). -147).

Table (2-1) shows that public spending in 2004 amounted to (32,117) billion dinars, with a contribution rate of (60.33%) of the gross domestic product, while in 2005 there was a decrease in public spending, which amounted to (26,374) billion dinars, with a negative change rate of (- 17.88%), with a contribution rate of 35.87% to the GDP. In the following years, public spending continued to increase, as it amounted to (39030) billion dinars in 2007, with a positive change rate (58%), a decrease in the rate of change of GDP (16.60%), and a decrease in the rate of change The contribution of public spending to the gross domestic product (35.02%) and the reason for this is due to the imbalance of the security situation in Iraq. In 2008, public spending amounted to (59402) billion dinars, with an annual change rate of (52.20%) and a contribution rate to the GDP amounted to (37.83%), so public spending witnessed a decline (2009) to record an amount of (52567) billion dinars and an annual rate of change A negative rate of (-11.51 %) and a contribution rate to the gross domestic product amounted to (40.24%) and this is attributed in public spending to the result of the global financial crisis and the accompanying drop in demand for oil and the collapse of its prices in global markets and the reduction of the volume of commercial activity, which negatively impacted on The volume of public expenditures, which made it possible to follow a contractionary fiscal policy. In 2011, public spending witnessed an increase to record (69,640) billion dinars, with a positive annual change rate of (8.22%), as its contribution to the gross domestic product amounted to (32.04%) to continue The increase in public spending until 2013, so that public spending for the year 2012 recorded an amount of (90,375) billion dinars, with a rate of change of (29.77%), while public spending recorded an amount of (106873) billion dinars for the year 2013 and a rate of change of (18.26%) and a contribution rate of the output

**Table 1: the evolution of public spending and GDP in Iraq for the period (2004-2020)
(billion dinars)**

years	public expenditure	Annual rate of change %	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at current prices	GDP change rate	Share of public spending to gross domestic product (GDP)
2004	32117	----	53235	----	60.33
2005	26374	(17.88)	73533	38.13	35.87
2006	38806	47.14	95587	29.99	40.60
2007	39030	0.58	111455	16.60	35.02
2008	59402	52.20	157026	40.89	37.83
2009	52576	(11.51)	130643	(16.80)	40.24
2010	64351	22.42	162064	24.05	39.71
2011	69640	8.22	217327	34.10	32.04
2012	90375	29.77	254225	16.98	35.55
2013	106873	18.26	273587	7.62	39.06
2014	83556	(21.82)	266332	(2.65)	31.37
2015	70396	(15.75)	194680	(26.90)	36.16
2016	67067	(4.73)	196924	1.15	34.06
2017	75489	12.56	221665	12.56	34.06
2018	80872	7.13	268918	21.32	30.07
2019	111723	38.15	276157	2.69	40.46
2020	76081	(31.90)	219768	(20.42)	34.62

Source: From the work of the researcher with accreditation

- Central Bank of Iraq, Department of Statistics and Research, Annual Statistical Bulletin for the period (2004-2020).

- Central Bank of Iraq, Statistical website: <https://cbiraq.org/Default.aspx>

The rate of change, wherever it is found in the study, was calculated according to the following formula:

- Annual rate of change % = (previous year in value - current year in value) / (previous year in value) x 100

-The values in parentheses () are negative

The gross domestic product amounted to (39.06%) and this is due to an increase in oil exports as well as an improvement in crude oil prices. As for the period 2014-2016, public spending witnessed a significant successive decline to record (83,556, 70396 and 67067) billion dinars, with a negative rate of change, respectively. Its percentage amounted to (21.82%), -15.75% and (4.73%) and this decrease is attributed to the terrorist groups' acquisition of parts of Iraq's regions. As for the years from 2017-2019, public spending witnessed a successive increase to reach (75,489 and 80872 and 111,723) billion dinars, with a positive change rate of (12.56%), (7.13%) and (38.15%), and this is due to the result of the improvement in international oil prices, which was reflected on public spending through the construction of infrastructure. As for the year 2020, public spending witnessed In Iraq, a decrease to record an amount of (76081)

billion dinars, with a negative change rate of (-31.90%), and a percentage of its contribution to the gross domestic product (34.62%).

Figure 1: the evolution of public spending and GDP in Iraq for the period (2004-2020)

Source: The researcher's work is based on the data in Table (1).

2- Public Revenue Analysis:

Through Table (2), it is clear that the general revenues for the year 2004 amounted to (32981) billion dinars, with a contribution rate of (61.95%) of the gross domestic product. As for the years from 2005-2008, it witnessed a successive increase of (4,0502), (49054), (54597) and (80250) billion dinars, and the percentage of public revenues' contribution to the gross domestic product (55.08%) (51.32%) (48.99%) (51.11%) respectively. This is attributed to the rise in oil prices because the main source of public revenues is oil revenues. In 2009, public revenues decreased, amounting to (55,208) billion dinars, with a negative rate of change (-31.20%), and a contribution rate of (42.26%) to the gross domestic product. This decline is due to the drop in oil prices due to the global financial crisis. As for the years 2010- 2012 witnessed an increase compared to the previous year, as public revenues amounted to (69520), (99997) and (119465) billion dinars, with a positive change rate of (25.92%) (43.84%) (19.47%) and a contribution rate of (42.90) to the gross domestic product (%) (46.01%) (46.99%) respectively. This increase in revenues is attributed to the increase in oil production capacities, etc. Mother.

Table 2: Percentage of the contribution of public revenues from GDP in Iraq for the period (2004-2020) (billion dinars)

years	general revenue	The rate of change of public revenue	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at current prices	Percentage of the contribution of public revenues to the gross domestic product
2004	32981	-----	53235	61.95
2005	40502	22.80	73533	55.08
2006	49054	21.12	95587	51.32
2007	54597	11.30	111455	48.99
2008	80250	46.99	157026	51.11
2009	55208	(31.20)	130643	42.26
2010	69520	25.92	162064	42.90
2011	99997	43.84	217327	46.01
2012	119465	19.47	254225	46.99
2013	113765	(4.77)	273587	41.58
2014	105386	(7.37)	266332	39.57
2015	66469	(36.93)	194680	34.14
2016	54408	(18.15)	196924	27.63
2017	77334	42.14	221665	34.89
2018	106568	37.80	268918	39.63
2019	107566	0.94	276157	38.95
2020	63198	(41.25)	219768	28.76

Source: From the researcher's work based on:

- **Central Bank of Iraq, Department of Statistics and Research, Annual Statistical Bulletin for the period (2004-2020).**

- **Central Bank of Iraq, Statistical website: <https://cbiraq.org/Default.aspx>**

- **Values in parentheses () are negative**

As for the years 2013-2015, oil revenues decreased to an amount of (113,765), (105386) (66469) and (54408) billion dinars, with a negative change rate, reaching (-4.77) (-7.37) (- (-36.93))) -18.15%) respectively. This is attributed to the decrease in oil production due to the occupation of the oil production fields by terrorist organizations, in addition to the decrease in the price of crude oil. The years from 2017-2019 witnessed an increase in revenues, reaching (77334), (106568) and (107566) billion This is due to the increase in global demand for oil, which led to a rise in crude oil prices. In 2020, public revenues decreased to reach 63,198 billion dinars, with a negative change rate of (41.25%) and a contribution rate of (28.76%) to the gross domestic product. The reason for the decline is due to the deteriorating health situation in the world, the spread of the Corona epidemic, and the decrease in demand for crude oil.

Figure 2: Percentage of the contribution of public revenues to the GDP for the period 2004-2020

Source - prepared by the researcher based on the data of Table No. (2)

The third axis - analysis of unemployment rates in Iraq for the period (2004-2020)

The labor market in Iraq is characterized by a high rate of workers, and this matter does not differ from neighboring countries, and the most important characteristics of the Iraqi labor market is the high rate of growth of supply for workers, and this is due to the high rate of population and workforce growth compared to the low rate of growth of demand for work due to the lack of allocations Prepared for investment due to wars, security and political turmoil and the global crisis that swept the world and Iraq in particular. The high unemployment rates in Iraq came as a result of several reasons, the most important of which are: the high rate of population growth, and that the Iraqi economy is one-sided (rentier), i.e. the dependence of revenues mainly on crude oil, as well as weak educational planning, i.e. not linking the outputs of educational institutions to the labor market, As well as the weak role of the private sector in absorbing graduates (Abdul Karim, 2012: 65).

Table 3: Evolution of unemployment rates in Iraq for the period (2004-2020)

Years	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Unemployment rate %	28	23	20	19	16	14	12	17	14
Years	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	
Unemployment rate %	8	9.9	16	12	14	11	10	1	

Source: From the researcher’s work based on:

- Ministry of Planning, Central Agency for Statistics and Information Technology, Statistical Group for the Years (2004-2020).
- Anbar and Nineveh governorates were not included in the statistical group for the years (2015-2016).

Table (3) shows that the year 2004 witnessed the highest unemployment rate during the research period, as it reached (28.1%), and this is high compared to some years that followed the year (2004). Subsequently, in 2005, the unemployment rate in Iraq reached (23.3%), and the unemployment rate started to decrease. 12.3%), and the reason for this successive decline is the rise in the general revenues of the federal budget in Iraq and the achievement of a surplus, which led to an increase in the state's expenditures, which positively affected by increasing employment in public institutions in order to address the problem of unemployment, as well as returning the dismissed politicians to government departments, Then the unemployment rate began to decline during the period (2012-2014) to reach (10%) in (2014) compared to 2012, which amounted to (14.3%), as a result of the improvement in the economic and security conditions during that period, and the unemployment rate increased in (2015).) to reach a percentage of (16.7%), and returns to This caused many economic and political challenges, as the recent developments represented by the unstable political situation, the continued deterioration of the security situation and the ongoing military operations against terrorist groups (ISIS) that occupied some Iraqi provinces and displaced the population from their areas, as well as the destruction and sabotage of the infrastructure of those provinces. Especially in light of the presence of some important oil fields in those governorates, then the unemployment rate gradually decreased in the years (2018, 2019) to reach (11.7%) (10.3%), due to the improvement of public revenues as a result of the rise in crude oil prices and the increase in spending, especially to the liberated governorates. As for the year 2020, the unemployment rate increased by 12%, due to the spread of the Corona disease, which swept the world and Iraq in particular, where a curfew was imposed and work was stopped in most government departments, except for service and security, as well as a complete cessation of work in the private sector.

Figure 3: shows unemployment rates in Iraq for the period (2004-2020)

Source: From the researcher's work based on Table (3)

We note from Figure (3) and by referring to the public revenue data, it becomes clear that there is an inverse relationship between public revenue and the unemployment rate in Iraq. In 2015, public revenue decreased (66469 billion dinars, which led to an increase in the unemployment rate for the same year to reach 16.7%). In 2019, public revenues increased to reach a value of (107566) billion dinars, and the unemployment rate decreased to reach (10.2%).

1- Government measures aimed at reducing unemployment through the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs

There are a set of measures followed by the government, including the following:

1-1-Department of Employment and Loans: This department aims to reduce unemployment and poverty by creating job opportunities for the unemployed or by granting them soft loans for the purpose of investing in several industrial, agricultural and commercial fields. The categories covered by this program are (Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs, Department of Employment and Loans, Department of planning)

- Unemployed groups registered in a database, including men and women, and they do not have any fixed resource, they are given soft loans to help them provide suitable job opportunities.

The groups covered by the Community Rehabilitation Fund, and this idea was put forward in (1995) in coordination between the International Labor Organization and the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs, and a group of marginalized groups were merged, namely, women who provide for their families, released prisoners, the disabled, and wives with severe disabilities within the ages (20-60).) a year through the establishment of income-generating projects by giving them loans of up to (3,000,000) dinars.

- Categories covered by the Small Income-Generating Projects Support Fund, and this fund was established by issuing Law No. (10) of (2012) and the capital of this fund is estimated (150) billion dinars. This fund provides financing for small and medium-sized projects for the unemployed and those registered in the database for age groups (18) - (45) The amount of the loan is according to the project, provided that it does not exceed (20) million dinars.

The categories covered by the poverty reduction mechanism, and that this program was established in (2007) and is concerned with small projects only for individuals who are below the poverty line, including displaced, divorced, unemployed and widowed within the ages of (18-55) and that the value of the loan ranges from (5-10) million Dinars according to the nature of the project.

Table 4: Programs of the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs that aim to reduce unemployment for the period (2004-2020)

Years	The number of unemployed registered in the Department of Employment and Loans	Preparing the unemployed beneficiaries in the Department of Employment and Loans
2004	182905	-----
2005	193854	-----
2006	231543	-----
2007	294321	9347
2008	220345	23369
2009	131703	28043
2010	173273	18695
2011	325747	13086
2012	126090	7478
2013	118045	1900
2014	59731	6434
2015	114532	16946
2016	70803	4747
2017	532467	2536
2018	450000	3051
2019	469345	4381
2020	279831	3716

Source from the researcher's work based on:

- Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs, Annual Statistical Collection, Different Years (2004-2020)

It is noted from Table (4) that the number of registered unemployed people is small compared to the real number of the level of unemployment and the unemployed, and the reason for this is due to the unwillingness to register in the database as unemployed, either because they are ignorant of the mechanisms of work of the Ministry of Labor departments in the way they are registered, or due to lack of confidence In obtaining interest in light of the increase in favoritism and bribery to obtain a subsidy or a loan, the number of registered unemployed doubled in the years (2017) (2018) (2019) and the reason for this increase is the cumulative number of previous years, but in (2020) the number decreased to (279831) This decrease is due to the spread of the Corona epidemic and the disruption of the work of the state departments from performing work due to the prevention of movement and roaming. As for soft loans, they began to work on (15/4/2007), and in 2012 a fund was established to support income-generating projects that were approved with the approval of And the support of the Council of Ministers, and then it was approved by the Iraqi parliament, and it was published in the Official Gazette by Law No. (10) for the year (2012) and it is still continuing to grant loans.

Figure 4: Number of registered unemployed and beneficiaries in the Department of Employment and Loans

Source: From the researcher's work based on the data in Table (4).

1-2- Vocational Training Department

This department started its work in the Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs in coordination with the International Labor Organization in the year (1972), as there were (6) training centers and after (2003) the Ministry of Labor started developing and rehabilitating the training centers and equipping them with devices and equipment, as the number of training centers in the department reached Vocational training (37) centers, and these centers were able to train thousands of young people in various professions (maintenance of electrical appliances, sewing, carpentry, and other professions), and the duration of the course ranges between (2-6) months, and the graduate obtains a certificate of professional competence, as well as About a reward of (10000) dinars for each training day, and one of the goals of the ministry that it is trying to reach through the establishment of these courses by absorbing the unemployed and dropouts from the study, and finding job opportunities for them by gaining experience and skill in various fields of work, as the Vocational Training Department describes the courses Which you rate to (Karim, 2019: 59):

Self-capacity building courses.

- Educational courses that include (English language, computer skills, literacy).
- Pioneering courses related to life skills and getting to know the business world.
- Courses that include training on professions required in the labor market, including (car electrician, leather industries, sewing, aluminum, electric elevators, textiles, mobile maintenance, computer maintenance and other professions and crafts).

We note from Table (2-17) that the number of registered persons in the Vocational Training Department for the year (2004) amounted to (6321), to continue the increase in the number of people who received vocational training courses until the year (2008) to reach (50591) and this increase is attributed to the increase in the number of trainees. The improvement of public revenues during that period, as well as the increase in financial allocations for this department, to witness a decrease in the number of trainees in (2009) to reach (9168), and the reason for this decline was the global financial crisis in that period, which led to a decrease in allocations to the Training Department, to continue to rise until the year (2017) to reach (23971), which is the highest year in which there was a significant increase in the number of trainees, and the reason for this increase was the improvement in revenues as a result of the improvement in international oil prices. The Corona epidemic, which affected the world as a whole and Iraq in particular

Table 5: shows the number of graduates from the Vocational Training Department (2004-2020)

Years	Preparing graduates from the Vocational Training Department	Years	Preparing graduates from the Vocational Training Department
2004	6321	2013	19040
2005	8432	2014	18755
2006	11786	2015	12077
2007	40877	2016	18100
2008	50591	2017	23971
2009	9168	2018	3224
2010	14106	2019	9321
2011	14520	2020	6272
2012	14380		

Source from the researcher's work based on:

- Ministry of Labor and Social Affairs, Vocational Training Department, Planning Department, different years (2004-2020)

Figure 5: Preparation of graduates of vocational training courses in Iraq for the period 2004-2020

The source is from the researcher's work based on the data in Table (5).

Conclusions

1. The fiscal policy has a role in reducing unemployment rates in Iraq during the study period, which shows the role it plays in addressing unemployment, which tended to decline during the research period.
2. The security, political and economic turmoil that Iraq was subjected to during the research period in all areas and the control of terrorist groups over some provinces, as it became obligatory for the makers of economic decisions in the country to take special decisions on both sides of expenditures and revenues and directing those financial resources to service projects that reduce unemployment.
3. The analysis shows that there is an inverse relationship between public expenditures and public revenues on the one hand, and the unemployment rate on the other hand. An increase in public expenditures leads to a decrease in unemployment rates at the same time.
4. Increasing dependence on oil revenues to cover public expenditures makes the Iraqi economy more vulnerable to external economic crises that occur in importing countries, which affects the country and impedes the course of growth and targeted economic development.
5. The public spending in the Iraqi economy has achieved very high levels, especially at the levels of current spending, because government spending is affected by oil revenues, which provided the state with large financial revenues. according to the interests of the people.

Recommendations

1. Rationalizing spending by reducing employment in government institutions and focusing on sectors that work to create added value (productive institutions), which leads to the revival of the Iraqi economy.
2. The public expenditures in Iraq are the largest proportion of them destined for current expenditures, so it is necessary to increase investment expenditures that lead to the expansion of production capacities and increase of production, and this increases the provision of opportunities for the unemployed and reduces unemployment.
3. The necessity of assisting the unemployed and low-income groups in finding the necessary financing means to set up small-sized projects that depend on the element of work and low cost.
4. Working to increase the average per capita income of citizens by raising the efficiency of workers and increasing their productivity, linking wages to productivity, establishing productive government projects with the aim of increasing the job opportunity, encouraging small projects for the purpose of generating income, as well as seeking to abandon privatization programs that would lead to Unemployment rises.

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